

The current problems of the state policy on the financial support of the Ukraine's security forces

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Annotation. The current problems of the state policy regarding the financial security of the state security forces are highlighted. The factors (codes of the programme classification of expenditures and crediting of the state budget), which influence the formation of opportunities, effectiveness of actions and existence of a certain security force of the state, are identified; the estimation of their importance with an a priori ranking method is offered and the approach to identification of the most important factors (codes of the programme classification of expenditures and crediting of the state budget) is justified. The obtaining of an instrument by which an institution which implements a state policy on the financial security of the security forces can use the scientific approach to estimate and separate the most important factors which influence the formation of capabilities, the effectiveness of actions and the existence of a certain security force.

In our opinion, public administration in the field of national security of Ukraine is an organized process of managing, regulating and controlling the state bodies to ensure the stable development of society, the response to urgent threats, as well as the crisis prevention. Such process is implemented through the public policy – an action programme or a system of focused actions. The National Security Strategy of Ukraine, implemented by The Presidential Decree No. 28/2015 by May 26, 2015, lists such current threats of the national security as insufficient resources and inefficient use of resources in the security and defense sector. There, among the main directions of the state policy in the mentioned area, the application of a programme-focused approach of determining the amount of financial and logistical resources, which are necessary for the effective functioning of the bodies of the security and defense sector and the defense-industrial complex, is identified [1]. The same point is repeated in the Concept of Development of the Security and Defense Sector, introduced by Presidential Decree No. 92/2016 by March 14, 2016 [2].

Unfortunately, there is no single normative legal document for all the security forces which defines strategic, operational objectives and expected results of the state policy for reforming the financial security system. At the same time, it should be noticed that Article No. 35 of the Law on National Security of Ukraine defines the fact that the amount of the expenditures for financing the security and defense sector should be at least 5% of the planned amount of gross domestic product, of which at least 3% should be for financing the Defense Forces [3]. That is, less than 2% should be given to all the security forces. All of

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the above determines the urgent relevance of the research of the problems of financial security for the security forces in the direction of the implementation of the state policy in the area of the national security of Ukraine.

The estimation of the condition of the components of the security and defense sector, namely the security forces, shows that its current condition cannot provide a guaranteed response to the current threats of the Ukraine's national security. For example, there are remaining such unsolved problems of public policy in the security and defense sector as:

the long-term financial and material provision of the security and defense components on a basis of remainder, the imperfection of the process of formation, coordination and interaction of the security and defense components in solving the common national security tasks;

the incompleteness of the process of building of the effective system of resource management in crisis situations, which threaten the national security;

the imperfect system of planning and joint use of troops (forces) and facilities, their training and provision.

The most relevant threats in the medium term will remain: crisis in the national economy, ineffectiveness of the anti-crisis measures, which lead to the depletion of the financial resources of the state, limit the state's ability to financially support the implementation of national security policy.

The overcoming of these public policy problems is being provided by the deliberate reforming and development of the security and defense sector, including the security forces of the state, with the introduction of the unified system of planning and management of resources based on modern European and Euro-Atlantic approaches, which will lead to increase its institutional and structural balance and to build the effective integrated and multifunctional national security tools.

The purpose of the study is to justify a tool with the help of which the most important codes of programme classification of expenditures and crediting of the state budget can be estimated and separated, influencing the formation of capabilities, effectiveness of actions and the existence of the state security forces.

In the modern science, the problems of the logistic and financial security of the security forces and the defense forces have received much attention [4-9]. It should be noticed that there are the significant contribution and the scientific results obtained by domestic scientists in the area of logistic: V. Kivlyuk has investigated the problems of forming the policy and strategy of functioning of the main types of security of Ukraine's defense complex; I. Romanchenko and V. Shuykinin have justified the opinion [10] on the development of the logistic system of the Armed Forces of Ukraine; O. Khazanovich and S. Tregubenko have published their research on modeling of logistic systems; M. Goloborodko, V. Biletov, V. Galagan have developed and published the formalized model of the logistic support of the troops (forces). Much attention was paid on the improvement of the processes of the logistic management of the military units [5,11,12]. The impact of the limited financing, including those, which are spent on food security, was investigated by S. Pavlenko [13]. At the same time, the methods of the budget funds distribution between the codes of programme classification of expenditures and crediting of the state budget to the needs of the National Guard of Ukraine, as an integral part of the security and defense sector of Ukraine, remain insufficiently explored. The biggest interest belongs to the labour [14], which justifies the methodology of work of the chief of the ware service of the Territorial Department of the National Guard of Ukraine on the organization of the ware security of actions to maintain the legal regime of emergency. The particular attention is paid to determining the factors which influence the ware security of military

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personnel during actions to maintain the legal regime of emergency, assessing the significance of factors, using an a priori ranking method and proposing an approach to identify the most significant factors. In conducting the research, we use the generally accepted methodology and organization of the scientific research [15].

The factor refers to the condition, circumstance, variable, code of programme classification of expenditures and crediting of the state budget, which influences the formation of opportunities, effectiveness of actions or even the existence of the certain security force. Factors (codes of the programme classification of expenditures and crediting of the state budget), which influence the formation of opportunities, effectiveness of actions and the existence of the certain security force (for example, the National Guard of Ukraine), are determined according to the State budget using the method of the expert estimation. The method is based on receiving and processing the data, which was obtained from a survey of experts in the area. However, such a method makes it possible only to determine a set of factors without considering the amount of their impact. One of the methods, which allows us to choose the significant factors, is an a priori ranking method. The method is based on the ranking of factors (codes of the programme classification of expenditures and crediting of the state budget) in the decreasing order of their contributions for the final result. The contribution of a factor is estimated by the amount of the rank assigned to a particular factor in the ranking of all factors, taking into account their predicted impact on the optimization parameter. This method is widely used in various areas: military, economic, engineering, geological, etc.

An a priori ranking method, which is based on the peer review of the factors by a group of specialists in the area of the study, comes down to the following:

1. Determining the preliminary list of factors (codes of the programme classification of expenditures and crediting of the state budget, which are given in Table 1), which require ranking, based on the analysis of literary data, generalization of the available experience, questioning of experts etc.

2. Preparing a questionnaire, where should be given, preferably in a tabular form, a list of factors, the necessary explanations and instructions, the examples of filling in the questionnaires.

3. Completing and verifying the competence of the group of experts, who should be the specialists in the considered issues, but not personally interested in the results.

The expert competence can be verified through the tests, with the method of self-assessment or the benchmarking. During the testing, the percentage of the correct answers in the area related to the future estimation serves as a measure of the expert's competence. The self-assessment method is when the each expert candidate uses his/her scale to estimate his/her knowledge on a number of issues. The maximum score gets an issue which, according to the expert, he/she knows better than others, and the minimum one goes to the issue which he/she knows worse than others. Then all the other questions are estimated by the points from maximum to minimum and the average self-assessment of the expert and then the one of the expert group are displayed. This method also allows us to create sub-groups, if necessary, to examine the specific issues.

After the group is formed, the oral or written instruction of experts is conducted. The experts carry out an individual estimation of the suggested factors, during the process of which with the help of rankings the factors are arranged in the decreasing order by the level of their influence on the resulting sign or the object of study, which is considered the targeted function. The rank is indicated as a_{km} , where m is the expert's conditional number; k is a factor number. In this case, the factor which has the biggest impact is rated with the highest score, and the factor which has the least value is rated with the lower score etc.

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The received estimations should not be discussed with the other experts and are passed to the organizers of the examination. The examination results are held by the organizers of the examination. According to the results of the examination, the organization or the expert, who have conducted the expert survey, the suggestions for solving the specific problems are offered to the management of the system, or the results are transmitted without any comments.

Let us consider the example of the estimation of the impact of a number of factors (codes of the programme classification of expenditures and crediting of the state budget) on the activity of the National Guard of Ukraine as a component of the security and defense sector of Ukraine.

There were selected the seven factors for the expert estimation based on the analysis of the State Budget of Ukraine ($k = 6$):

- leadership and management of the security forces;
- ensuring the performance of tasks and functions by the the security forces;
- training of the personnel of the security forces for the higher education institutions;
- hospital care for the military personnel (employees) of the security forces in their own medical institutions;
- building (purchasing) the apartments for the military personnel (employees) of the security forces;
- expenditures for the security forces to implement the measures to improve the defense and the security of the state.

The following sequence of processing an a priori ranking results is recommended.

1. The individual ratings of all experts are summarized in an a priori ranking table.
2. The sum of the ranks of all experts for each factor is determined by the following formula:

$$D_k = \sum_{m=1}^n a_{km} = \sum_{m=1}^n a_{km}, \quad (1)$$

where m is a number of an expert, $m = 1, \dots, n$; $k = 1, \dots, c$ is a number of a factor.

3. The sum of the ranks and the average value of the sum of the ranks are calculated by the following formula:

$$d = \sum_{k=1}^c D_k = \sum_{k=1}^c D_k, \quad (2)$$

where d is a sum of the ranks of all factors; D_k is a sum of the ranks of the k -factor, $k = 1, \dots, c$.

$$\bar{d} = \frac{d}{k}, \quad (3)$$

where \bar{d} is a middle value of the sum of the ranks of all factors; D_k is a sum of the ranks of the k -factor, $k = 1, \dots, c$.

4. The correctness of filling in the table is checked:

– the maximum value of the sum of the ranks for each factor cannot be more than the product of the maximum possible rank by the number of experts, that is

$$\max D_k \leq (\max a_{km}) \cdot n, \quad (4)$$

– the minimum possible sum of the ranks for each factor cannot be less than the minimum rank multiplied by the number of experts, that is

$$\min D_k \geq (\min a_{km}) \cdot n, \quad (5)$$

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5. The specific weights of the factors for their impact on the targeted value are determined by the following formula:

$$q_k = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^g a_{km}}{\sum_{k=1}^g D_k} = \frac{D_k}{d}, \quad (6)$$

where q_k is the proportion of the impact of each factor on the targeted value.

6. Using the Kendall concordance coefficient, the level of consistency of the experts' opinions is estimated by the following formula:

$$W = \frac{12}{m^2(k^3 - k)} \sum_{k=1}^g \sum_{m=1}^g a_{km} - \frac{\sum_{k=1}^g D_k^2}{k} = \frac{12}{m^2(k^3 - k)} \sum_{k=1}^g \left((D_k - \bar{d})^2 \right), \quad (7)$$

The concordance coefficient can be 0 ≤ W ≤ 1. If it substantially differs from zero (W > 0,5), it can be considered that there is some consistency between the experts' opinions. If the concordance coefficient is inadequate (W < 0,5), the analysis of the reasons of the negative result is held. Such reasons may be: the unclear questioning or briefing, the incorrect choice of factors, the selection of the incompetent (or with little experience) experts, etc.

Depending on the results of such analysis, a decision is made to correct the examination, namely:

- involvement of the other experts.
- changing of the instruction;
- adjustment of the composition of factors.

In any case, re-examination of the former composition of the experts is not recommended.

7. Provided W > 0,5, the hypothesis about not accidental consent of experts is tested. For this procedure, the Pearson criterion is used, which is determined by the following formula:

$$C_r^2 = W \times (k - 1), \quad (8)$$

where C_r^2 is a the Pearson criterion coefficient; $(k - 1)$ is a number of freedom levels.

The calculated value of the coefficient is compared with the tabular value (at a significance level of 0.01), determined by the number of freedom levels $(k - 1)$. If the calculated value of the Pearson criterion coefficient is more than a tabular one ($C_r^2 > C_t^2$), and $W > 0,5$, then this indicates the fact that there is a significant similarity of the experts' opinions, the significance of the concordance coefficient and not not accidental consent of the experts' opinions.

To give a clear idea of the significance level of the factors, an a priori rank chart is constructed. When constructing a diagram, the abscess axis defines the factors in the increasing order of the sum of the ranks, and the ordinate axis defines the sum of the ranks.

Using the rank chart, the most influential factors can be identified and the factors which have a non-essential impact can be neglected. If the distribution of the influence level of the factors is even and monotonically decreases, it means that in the further process all the factors must be taken into account.

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In case of a rapid exponential decrease of the level of influence of the factors, the proportion of the factors may not be considered (i.e. excluded) in the further process. For this purpose, a threshold is determined by the method of the expert estimations, at which all the factors which have an impact value less than the established threshold are not taken into account. Or such threshold divides the factors into two groups: the main ones, which should be taken into account when preparing the decision, and the additional ones, which will increase the validity of the decision.

Therefore, the study has identified the factors (codes of the programme classification of expenditures and crediting to the state budget) which influence the formation of the opportunities, the effectiveness of actions and the existence of a certain security force of the state; the estimation of their significance using an a priori ranking method is offered and the approach to the selection of the most significant factors (codes of the programme classification of expenditures and crediting of the state budget) is justified.

Using of this method has both advantages and disadvantages. The advantages of an a priori ranking are: comparative simplicity of the organization of procedure and promptness of obtaining results. The disadvantages are: high dependence of results on the quality of organization of the examination and the selection of experts that is considered as subjectivity. In addition, when estimating the certain factors (measures) for a given system, experts use their previous experience or views (which is why expertise is called an a priori). Therefore, the correct formulation of the questions and the choice of the factors for a given system have particular importance and significantly affect the results of the examination.

The result of this work is obtaining a tool through which an institution which implements a state policy on the financial security of the security forces can, using a scientific approach, estimate and separate the most important factors (codes of the programme classification of expenditures and crediting of the state budget) which influence the formation of the opportunities, the effectiveness of the actions and the existence of the certain security force.

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